

Drug Overdoses in Detroit

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Risky Times, Risky Places

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Presentation Overview:

Goal: To better understand how elements of the physical environment can impact the occurrence of drug overdoses (ODs)

If we understand the locations at high risk for OD, we can develop targeted interventions

- Brief overview of the OD problem in US
- Data Issues: Different sources, different locations, different solutions
- Can Risk Terrain Modeling help us to better understand ODs?

Unprecedented OD crisis in US, fueled by rise in opioid use

CDC: Over 105,000 deaths in 12 month period; non-fatal ODs are higher (10/2022 - 11/2023)

Includes prescription opioids (hydrocodone, oxycodone, morphine), heroin, synthetic opioids (fentanyl); also cocaine and methamphetamine

Origins: 1990s, focus on pain management; rise in 'pill mills;' lack of coordinated monitoring

How many OD? The issue of Data

Three popular sources:

- Cause of death data from autopsies
- Hospital data: Discharge data, ER visits
- 911 Calls for Service

Different sources, different geographies

The Case of Detroit, MI

Detroit Demographics:

640k residents; median income \$36k; 1/3 of population below poverty line

How Many Overdoses?

- State of Michigan: 486 deaths in city limits (2021)
- MDHHS, 2020 (non-fatal):
 - 3,193 ER visits; 1,287 hospitalizations in Detroit
- 911 Calls for Service: 7,102 in 2022
 - Call Data: XY with off-set; day, time

Time Block	All Calls	% of Total Calls
0000-0359	1,303	18.39
0400-0759	841	11.87
0800-1159	607	8.57
1200-1559	1,010	14.26
1600-1959	1,601	22.60
2000-2359	1,723	24.32

Snapshot of Time

Most calls in evening, early morning hours

Why is time of day important?

- Relates to question of why people are taking drugs
- Is the use recreational? Or is it daily users / non-recreational?
(Madah-Amiri, et al. 2017)

Day of Week	All Calls	% of Total Calls
Sunday	1,119	15.79
Monday	914	12.90
Tuesday	934	13.18
Wednesday	965	13.62
Thursday	940	13.27
Friday	1,086	15.33
Saturday	1,127	15.91

Snapshot of Day of Week

Most on the weekends, but the difference is not that dramatic

Does this pattern suggest evidence of non-recreational use?

Month	All Calls	% of Total Calls
Jan	386	5.45
Feb	401	5.66
March	528	7.45
April	613	8.65
May	773	10.91
June	793	11.19
July	888	12.53
Aug	940	13.27
Sept	768	10.84
Oct	175	2.47
Nov	470	6.63
Dec	350	4.94

Snapshot of Seasonality

More prevalent in summer months

Note: October has missing data (approx. 20 days)

Temporal Summary

Most overdoses occur on the weekends, in the evenings / night time hours, and during the summer months

Overdose Locations

Individual data points versus optimized hot spot analysis results

Total area for hot spots: 7.76 square miles; 5 percent of the City of Detroit area

The largest contiguous hot spot in Downtown area was 7.0 square miles. Within this area, there were 1,203 overdoses, or 17 percent of the total number of over dose calls for service.

Earthstar Geographics | City of Windsor, Province of Ontario, Esri Canada,... 2 km Powered by Esri

Why So Many ODs?

What is it about the environment that makes overdoses more common?

Esri, ... 5 km Powered by Esri

City o... 5 km Powered by Esri

Co-location with Known Drug Areas?

Hot spots of dangerous drug arrests (in blue) versus Hot Spots of OD 911 calls for service (in red)

Arrest locations are helpful to understand hot spots in north /
northeast Detroit

Sales / possession arrests are not concentrated in Downtown area

- Journey to crime?
- Dark figure of crime at play?
- If only we had better data...

RTM Basics

Create a grid of cells for study area, add risk layers

- Risk layer 1: Bars
- Risk layer 2: ATM Locations
- Risk layer 3: Gas Stations

How does this look in reality?

Building the RTM

Some elements of the environment can generate or attract crime, overdoses, or other social problems

In this example, adding risk layers of bars & restaurants; hotels / motels; gas stations; casinos, and ATM locations

RTM focuses attention on risk factors and relative risk scores

ATMs	Dispensary	Laundromats	Restaurants / Bars
Bail Bonds	Education / Schools	Payday Loans	School Based Health Ctr
Beauty / Barber Shops	Fed Qual. Health Ctr	Parking Lots	Stadiums
Casinos	Food / Grocery	Pawn Shops	Tattoo Parlors
Check Cashing	Gas Stations	Religious Organizations	Vape Shops
Community Service Ctr	Hotels / Motels	Retail Stores	

Potential Risk Factors

- From ArcGIS Business Analyst; Classified by NAICS code
- Data year 2022
- $n = 23$

RTM Parameters

- Place Size = 50 meters
- Standard Value = 125 meters
- Tested for Proximity or Density
- Standard Value Multiplier x 3
- Whole Increments

RISK FACTOR	OPERATIONALIZATION	SPATIAL INFLUENCE	RELATIVE RISK
Retail Shops	Density	125	1.894
ATM Locations	Density	125	1.798
Restaurants / Clubs / Bars	Proximity	125	1.633
Religious Organizations	Proximity	375	1.519
Gas Stations	Proximity	125	1.519
Hotels / Motels	Proximity	375	1.498
Food / Grocery Stores	Proximity	250	1.294
Community Service Center	Proximity	375	1.265

RTM Results: Factors

Places within 125 meters of retail shops, ATM locations are almost 2x more likely to experience overdoses

Places near other factors are about 1.5 times more likely to experience overdoses

- Within 125m of a restaurant / bar / club
- Within 375m of a religious organization
- Within 125m of a gas station
- Within 375m of a hotel / motel
- Within 250m of a food / grocery store
- Within 375m of a Community Service Center

RTM Results: Relative Risk

125 meter places; Total number of places = 149,718

Relative Risk Statistics

- Range 1.00 - 31.49
- Mean 2.118 (SD = 2.02)
- 5,575 places have RR > 2 Standard Deviations; 3.72 percent of area of Detroit

Legend: Relative Risk Scores classified by Natural Breaks

What can be done?

RTM provides actionable results tailored to the needs of each community

Focus on the areas with highest vulnerability

- Where are our highest risk areas?
- What risk factors are there?
- Can these locations be targeted for life saving interventions?

Ex.: Focus on top 3 risk factors in highest risk areas

Retail shops; ATMs; Restaurants / Bars

Consider temporal dimension as well: Business operating hours vs. OD likelihood

Thank you for your time

Questions or comments, please contact Kim Lersch at klersch@usf.edu

For more information on Risk Terrain Modeling, please visit riskterrainmodeling.com

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Any questions regarding the content should be directed at Kim Lersch, University of South Florida, klersch@usf.edu

Works Cited	Listed in Order of Appearance
CDC, 2023	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. 2023. "Drug Overdose: Drug Basics." Last Modified August 22, 2023. Accessed 4/9/24. https://www.cdc.gov/drugoverdose/basics/
Pain Management	Addiction Center. 2014. "Pain clinics in America: The danger of pill mills." Accessed 4/7/2024. https://www.addictioncenter.com/community/pain-clinics-america-danger-pill-mills/
Detroit Demographics	City of Detroit. 2024. "City of Detroit Census Hub." Accessed 4/14/24. https://detroit-censusdata-detroitmi.hub.arcgis.com/
MDHHS, 2024	Michigan Department of Health & Human Services. 2024. "MiTracking: Michigan Environmental Public Health Tracking." State of Michigan. Accessed 2/5/24. https://mitracking.state.mis/
Detroit 911 Calls for Service	Detroit Open Data Portal, downloaded July 13, 2023. https://data.detroitmi.gov/
Madah-Amiri et al. 2017	Circumstances surrounding non-fatal opioid overdoses attended by ambulance services. Drug and Alcohol Review 36(3): 288-294. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1111%2Fdar.12451

Included Media

Videvo, Panning Across Silhouetted Detroit Skyline

<https://www.videvo.net/video/panning-across-silhouetted-detroit-skyline/6093/#rs=video-box>

UAB Birmingham Emergency Room

<https://www.uab.edu/police/about/divisions-and-units/hospital-precinct>

Police Lights

US Dept of State,
<https://www.state.gov/bureaus-offices/under-secretary-for-management/bureau-of-administration/office-of-emergency-management/>

Drug Image

<https://www.healthline.com/health/drug-overdose>

Coroner's Office

B. Barnum, CNN Health
<https://images.app.goo.gl/o3RYT41PUxkGLiCQ9>

RTM Basics

Lersch, K. (2014).
Understanding domestic violence using risk terrain modeling: Does place matter? *ACJS Today*, 39 (4): 21-34.

Naloxone Vending Machine

The Discount Vending Store
<https://www.discountvending.com>